

Multielemental speciation : Green methodologies for analysis of environmental samples[†]

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Abstract : Chemical speciation analysis has attracted great interest not only in analytical chemistry but also in other fields such as toxicology, food products, biology and ecology. The development of green strategies in chemical speciation has become highly provocative in current research. The article comprehensively reviews selected green methodologies developed by different researchers and future trend to study multielemental species present in environmental samples. Majority of the multispeciation analyses have been done by applying atomic spectrometry of which ICPMS is the method of choice because it gives additional advantages in respect of high sample throughput, sensitivity and the possibility of isotope measurement.

Keywords : Review, multielemental speciation, green methodologies, environmental sample analysis.

Introduction

Speciation analysis is described by the IUPAC as analytical methodologies of identifying and/or measuring the amount(s) of one or more individual chemical species in a sample. In other words, speciation is the identification and quantification of individual physico-chemical forms of elements present in different matrices¹.

Trace element concentration has been increasingly significant in various areas including environmental samples. No doubt, a trace element can often exist in a variety of chemical forms, which manifest different chemical, toxicological and biological activities. They depict the bioavailability, distribution and transport of the element in a living organism or in the environment. Evidently, there is a requirement for rapid and robust analytical tools to perform chemical speciation².

The improvement of trace element sampling and analysis techniques especially during the last decade of previous century and afterwards has tremendously increased our knowledge of trace element cycling and biogeochemistry in aquatic systems³. On the other hand, from the literature data and observation of current trends in chemical analysis and monitoring, it is evident that rapid progress has been made in the development of analytical methodo-

logies that assure observation of the principles of green analytical chemistry⁴.

The different steps of analytical procedures for analysis of environmental samples, for example, involve sampling, preservation, transport, sample preparation, analyte preconcentration, separation and finally determination. The transition from classical analytical chemistry to green analytical chemistry involves avoiding as many steps as possible, especially those concerning the shifting of samples from their original environment to laboratory, together with development of the researchers' mindset from drastic methods of sample digestion or analyte extraction to environmentally friendly ones, using much reduction of energy and consumption of reagents. In many cases, such transitions adduce simplification of matrix problems and excellent possibilities for characterization of specific chemical species originally extant in the samples and thus improve the analytical parameters⁵.

Majority of the speciation analyses outlined by Das *et al.* portray mono- or multi-species of single elements and some papers characterize determination of multielements in solid matrices⁶, biological fluids⁷, fly ash⁸, aqueous solutions⁹, marine samples¹⁰, miscellaneous samples^{11,12}. Recent efforts to develop green applications

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to all fields of chemistry have started to receive attention from academic perspective as well as practical applications. It is not always possible to use the greenest methods but the greenness profile in the National Environmental Methods Index (NEMI) database can guide to develop greener methods¹³. The object of this review article is to consolidate selected multispeciation analyses with special reference to green methodologies and to enumerate the future trend in this promising area of research.

Methodologies

In application areas such as environmental sample analysis, sample preparation is sometimes a bottleneck where powerful hyphenated systems in instrumental analysis of the final extracts contrast sharply with traditional high reagent consumption, large-scale, time-consuming and labor-intensive procedures. With this end in view, green analytical procedures have been used to extract and concentrate analytes. For example, in comparison to classical liquid-liquid extraction, extractions by using ultrasound, microwave, supercritical fluid, membranes and cloud point have been reported in which use of organic solvent could be reduced or avoided¹⁴.

With the introduction of chromatographic separation procedures, dramatic improvements in speciation along with better sensitivity can be achieved. Among nonchromatographic techniques, solid phase extraction (SPE) has been widely employed because it is convenient, economical, easy to operate, time saving, and environmentally friendly. Moreover, SPE offers the advantages of high sensitivity due to possibility of performing simultaneous enrichment step and versatility, since different substrates interact with different metal species¹⁵.

Complete automation of the analytical process, from field-sampling to instrumental measurement has been possible with on-line introduction of samples. This opportunity offers an excellent possibility for solving the problems related to multielemental speciation e.g. reducing the risks of sample storage, carrying out the pretreatment step, etc. On-line strategies for the speciation studies are very significant in environmental sample analysis in order to obtain actual data on natural systems⁹.

On the basis of the information available in the literature, multielement speciation can be classified into four groups depending on whether the chemical species are

reactive or non-reactive viz. organic and inorganic species¹⁶⁻²⁰, cationic and anionic species²¹⁻²⁵, species with different oxidation states²⁶⁻²⁸ and species with different chemical forms²⁹⁻³². Typical methodologies for multielemental species belonging to different groups in environmental samples are presented in Table 1.

Majority of the multielement speciation work has been done in the area of organic and inorganic species of the elements which are very significant from toxicological point of view. The matrix in which they have been studied extensively is water^{17,18} but sediment^{19,20} and other matrices have been investigated. The green speciation procedures reveal that high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major separation technique applied for such speciation which is followed by gas chromatography (GC). Among the multielemental detection techniques, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICPMS) has been widely applied.

Flow injection analysis (FIA) supported on SPE coupled with HPLC²², size exclusion chromatography (SEC) coupled with ICPMS²⁴ are examples of green methods for cationic and anionic species in natural water and human serum with nanogram to picogram level limits of detection.

Multispeciation studied for elements with variable oxidation states in environmental samples include As, Se, Sb, Cr and Te in matrices like water^{26,27} and fly ash²⁸.

Species of different chemical forms have been successfully studied by sequential extraction procedure. The extraction sequence proposed by Tessier *et al.*³³ has been modified in a greener way and applied to soil³², sediment^{29,31} and fly ash³⁰ samples.

It is evident from Table 1, multispeciation analysis is accomplished using a wide range of analytical procedures. Most of these belong to hyphenated techniques containing a chromatographic separation and a highly sensitive atomic spectrometric detection. Sometimes derivatization is followed by chromatographic separation. The limitation of UV-Vis spectrophotometry, neutron activation analysis (NAA), atomic spectrometry viz. atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) and atomic fluorescence spectrometry (AFS) is that there is no possibility of simultaneous multielement analysis. So use of ICPMS, inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry

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Table 1. Outlines of typical green methodologies for multielemental speciation in environmental samples

Species	Sample	Methodology	Ref.
Org., inorg. species of Mn, Mg, Zn, Fe, Al	Tea	Tea leaf extract with boiling water separated by HPLC; Mn, Mg, Zn and Fe determined by on-line ICP AES while Al by off-line ETAAS	16
Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Pb species of humic substances	Natural water	Humic substances isolated by sorption on XAD 8 or by ultrafiltration and metals analyzed by total reflection XRF	17
Hg ^{II} , organo-Hg, Se ^{IV} , Se ^{VI}	Natural, certified water	Speciation of Hg based on the inhibiting effect of its species on the urease-catalyzed hydrolysis of urea and resulting ammonia determined fluorimetrically; speciation of Se effected by preconcentration of its species on Hg-film deposited on glassy carbon working electrode in a flow cell, analyzed by cathodic and anodic stripping voltammetry	18
Alkyl-Hg, -Sn, -Pb	Sediment	Sediment suspended in water, adjusted to pH 5, alkylated with sodium tetraethyl borate and extracted into hexane, analyzed by GC-ICPMS	19
Bu Et-Sn, Me-Sn, Me-Hg	Fish, sediment	After ethylation of the species, the resulting compounds purged into cryogenic trap containing 3% OV-101 on Chromosorb HP cooled in liquid N ₂ , volatile components analyzed for metals by AAS	20
UO ₂ ²⁺ , Th ⁴⁺	Mineral water	SPE using 9-phenyl-3-fluorone chelates of the metals adsorbed on Duolite XAD 761; ICPMS detection	21
Pb ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺	Drinking water	On-line tetra-(4-bromophenyl)-porphyrin sorbed on RP-C ₁₈ -column; HPLC analysis	22
REEs	Marine biological tissues	Ultrasound-assisted extraction in 3% (v/v) HNO ₃ + 2% (v/v) HCl medium; ICPMS detection	23
Cd ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	Human serum	Proteins with different molecular mass separated by SEC; ICPMS detection	24
AsO ₃ ³⁻ , AsO ₄ ³⁻ , SeO ₃ ²⁻ , SeO ₄ ²⁻	Atmospheric particulate matter	Chelating solvent-based pressurized liquid extraction; HPLC-HG AFS analysis	25
As ^{III} , As ^V , Cr ^{VI}	Drinking, waste water	Simultaneous determination of the species by Ion Chromatography coupled to ICPMS	26
As ^{III} , As ^V , Sb ^{III} , Sb ^V	Natural water	Simultaneous determination of the species by hydride generation followed by GC with photoionization detection	27
As ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Se ^{IV}	Fly ash leachates	Acidified leachates divided into 4 parts : in 1st part As ^{III} and Sb ^{III} coprecipitated with dibenzylcarbamate followed by NAA determination; in 2nd part conversion of total As and Sb into hydrides, adsorption on activated carbon followed by NAA; in 3rd part Se ^{IV} reduced to Se, adsorbed on activated carbon followed by NAA; in 4th part total Se determined after refluxing with HCl followed by treatment as per 3rd part	28
Al, V, Cr, Ni, Co, Cu, Zn, As, Rb, Sr, Mo, Ag, Cd, Sb, Pb	Automobile exhaust, pond sediment	Microwave-assisted sequential extraction into 5 fractions; ICPMS detection	29
Zn, Cu, As, Mn	Fly ash	Microwave-assisted sequential extraction into 4 fractions; ICPMS detection	30
Cd, Zn, Pb	River bottom deposit	Microwave-assisted 3-stage and 5-stage extractions; FAAS detection	31
Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, V, Zn	Soil	Microwave-assisted 3-stage BCR sequential extractions; ETAAS detection	32

(ICPAES) and other multielement detection has been adopted.

Now-a-days, ICPMS has become the main atomic technique used for specific on-line elemental detection in speciation analysis due to its low detection limits, easy coupling to separation techniques and the ability to perform isotope dilution mass spectrometry (IDMS) calculations. Additionally, the use of IDMS with multiple tracers allows the detection and correction of interconversion reactions between the different species of the same element³⁴.

Future trend

It has been noticed above that liquid chromatography is the preferred technique for the coupling of a separation protocol to ICPMS when applied to trace element speciation in environmental samples. The coupling of HPLC to ICPMS is very convenient as the flow rates used in HPLC are compatible with those used by most of ICPMS nebulizers. Coupling of GC with ICPMS shows better resolution and sensitivity than HPLC ICPMS. GC coupled with either quadrupole or sector field (SF) instruments provide a solution for multielemental speciation of elements like Hg and As. In fact, SF ICPMS coupled with GC is more suitable for more demanding applications where lowest limits of detection and highest sensitivity would be required³⁵. It is evidenced that present scenario in green multielemental speciation incorporates the hyphenation/coupling of different analytical instruments by adding more than one detector. Few examples are cited below.

The presence of metal(loid) organic compounds in matrices of the environment has increased over the past decades due to human activities. Using hydride generation (HG)/LT-GC/ICPMS technique, it is possible to speciate organic compounds of 12 trace elements viz. Ge, As, Se, Mo, Sn, Sb, Te, I, W, Hg, Pb and Bi simultaneously in environmental samples such as municipal waste deposit. The method performs satisfactory separation of 26 species with absolute detection limits in the range 0.1–0.6 pg³⁶.

Solid phase microextraction (SPME), an alternative approach to liquid-liquid extraction, is a simple, fast, solvent-free technique combining sampling, extraction, concentration and sample introduction in a single device.

Headspace (HS) SPME has been applied for simultaneous determination of metal(loid) organic compounds viz. methylmercury, trimethyl-, triethyllead, monobutyl-, dibutyl- and tributyltin including inorganic mercury in sea water. The method consists of the ethylation with NaBEt₄, simultaneous HS SPME of the derivatives and finally GC MS analysis. The method is cheaper than GC ICPMS and has detection limits in the sub-ng L⁻¹ level³⁷.

A high performance in-the-field methodology was developed for sea, fresh and estuarine waters by isolating labile reactive species and stable organic complexes amenable to on-line UV photolysis. Coupled with ICPMS, it allowed simultaneous determination of Cd, Cu, Mn, Ni, Pb, U and Zn using a sample volume of 5 mL with detection limits ranging between 0.6 ng L⁻¹ for Cd and 33 ng L⁻¹ for Ni. The results also indicated that the organic complexation levels were high and unchanged for Cu in fresh and sea water samples, whereas difference was observed for remaining metals, suggesting organic ligands of different origin and/or their transformation/alteration along estuarine water mixing³⁸.

Simultaneous multielemental speciation was carried out by combining linear polyacrylamide coated capillary electrophoresis with inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (CE ICP TOFMS). Separation of 3 arsenic species and 2 cobalt cyanide complexes in aqueous solution needed less than 70 s. Absolute detection limits for various metal species were 1–20 pg for 20 nL injected sample volumes³⁹.

Two couplings i.e. HPLC UV cold vapor (CV)/HG AFS AFS and HPLC CV/HG ICPMS were applied for multispéciation studies of Hg²⁺, CH₃Hg⁺, AsO₃³⁻, MMA and AsO₄³⁻. The important feature was focused on separation and postcolumn on-line species treatment. The detection limits for various species by using AFS-AFS detection vary between 3–17 ng mL⁻¹ and those by using ICPMS detection are in the range 0.5–1.1 ng mL⁻¹. Although ICPMS detection is more sensitive, the combination of two AFS detectors proved to be a good alternative owing to their robustness and cheapness that make it applicable for routine analysis⁴⁰.

Speciation analysis of metal(loid)s in environmental samples has widely included the application of synchrotron X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS). However,

significant improvements have been reported when XAS is coupled with other structural probes and analytical speciation techniques. For example, for samples containing arsenic and selenium, HPLC ICPMS can provide details on the speciation of aqueous species, an environmental matrix that is usually beyond XAS with respect to detection limits. The results can be complimentary to XAS in order to explain the potential bioavailability, mobility and biogeochemical transformation of metal(loid)s⁴¹.

Rare earth elements (REEs) speciation is primarily important for long-term assessment of the performance of nuclear waste repositories, radionuclide migration in the environment and designing remediation processes viz. speciation and extraction of ¹⁵³Sm and ¹⁷⁷Lu from aqueous solution using polyoxometalates, specifically focusing on K₁₀(a₂-P₂W₁₇O₆₁) extracts both the radiolanthanides from nitric acid solution. The speciation is governed by the concentration of the analytes and pH (0–1). Using ³¹P NMR of Eu and Yb as probes for Sm and Lu respectively and luminescence of Eu analogs, the REEs species could be identified⁴².

For assessment of environmental safety, there has been continuous effort in the development of simple and robust procedures for the future to enable quantification of element species that impose health risk. In this regard, use of non-chromatographic procedures is gradually increasing. On the other hand, hyphenated techniques have already gained undisputed popularity. As mentioned earlier, ICPMS is going to be considered the most powerful detection technique not only due to its high sensitivity but also its compatibility with all different chromatographic/electrophoretic separations as well as its unique isotopic capabilities³⁴.

The main issue in multielemental speciation analysis is to assess native species distribution in environmental samples, so it is not surprising that synchrotron XAS⁴¹ and NMR⁴² may be incorporated, since they are the green methods requiring minimum or no sample treatment.

Conclusion

The field of speciation is changing and direction of research has shifted from the laboratory bench to real life, thus providing suitable methodologies and data about multispecies present in the environment. In this article a

literature survey of selected techniques used for green multielemental speciation of environmental samples has been depicted. Most of the methodologies using ICPMS detection are environmentally friendly alternatives to the classical methods based on sample digestion and/or analyte extraction. No doubt, it has been possible to illustrate the power and versatility of modern analytical instrumentation and their potentiality for minimizing the consumption of hazardous substances and the amount of waste generated during the laboratory work. After all ultimate scope of green analytical chemistry lies in its applicability.

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